

TRANSITION FROM A TRADITIONAL ECONOMY TO A GREEN ECONOMY PROVIDES SPEED OF STATE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the interdependence of ecology and economy, the impact and results of economic activity on the environment. The transition to "green economy" and its advantages will be highlighted in order to significantly reduce the environmental risks and degradation of nature caused by the country's economy and production. In addition, in this article, the experience of foreign countries in terms of eco-innovations and green investments in the transition to the "green economy" is widely studied.

It is known that the Republic of Uzbekistan has a high technical potential for energy production from renewable sources, 97% of which corresponds to the share of solar energy. In particular, the potential of solar energy production in the republic is 525-760 billion per year. kWh is The reason for this is that in our country there are an average of 320 sunny days a year and 3000 hours of active sunlight.

At the same time, the calculated potential of wind energy in Uzbekistan allows for deployment of devices with a capacity of 500 GW or 30 times more than the current energy system.

The conducted analyzes showed that there are interrelated problems and needs in ensuring an efficient, resource-efficient and ecologically safe economy in the face of climate change. In particular, accelerating industrialization and population growth are significantly increasing the economy's need for resources, as well as intensifying the negative anthropogenic impact on the environment and leading to an increase in greenhouse gas emissions.

First of all, let's talk about the "green" economy. The term "green economy" has come into use since the early 1990s, which supports a harmonious interaction between humanity and nature and simultaneously satisfies the needs of both. means a focused economy. In the international community, the strategy of "green" economy is considered as the main solution aimed at solving environmental, energy, food and economic problems that have a direct impact on human development.

In connection with the accession of Uzbekistan to the Paris Agreement on climate change, it undertook obligations related to the reduction of greenhouse gases and reducing the negative impact on the environment. Also, within the framework of the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, paragraph 250 of the state program adopted for 2019 envisages the development of this Strategy.

From this point of view, the priority directions of implementation of the strategy of transition to a "green" economy in Uzbekistan are to increase energy efficiency in the basic sectors of the economy, diversify the consumption of energy resources and develop the use of renewable energy sources, adapt to the consequences of climate change. and development of financial and non-financial mechanisms to mitigate them, increase efficiency of use of natural resources and preserve natural ecosystems, support "green" economy.

In addition, the following are the target indicators of the implementation of the Strategy:

- reducing greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 10 percent from the 2010 level;
- doubling the energy efficiency indicator and reducing the volume of carbon consumption of the gross domestic product;
- further development of renewable energy sources and increase their share to more than 25% of the total volume of electricity production;
- Providing up to 100% of the population and economic sectors with access to modern, cheap and reliable energy;
- modernizing the infrastructure of industrial enterprises, increasing their energy efficiency by at least 20 percent, and ensuring their stability due to the wider use of clean and environmentally safe technologies and industrial processes;
- expanding the production and use of motor fuel and motor vehicles with improved energy efficiency and ecological characteristics, as well as the development of electric transport;
- to significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, to introduce drip irrigation technology on an area of up to 1 million hectares, and to increase the yield of crops grown in them by 20-40%;
- achieving a neutral balance on land degradation;
- to achieve an increase in the average productivity of the main type of agricultural food production to 20-25%.

According to forecasts of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), if the modern way of production and consumption continues, by 2050, compared to the year 2000, 61 to 72 percent of the flora and fauna will be lost, and natural areas 7.5 mln. decreases to sq. m. (9). In 2015, according to the calculations of the team of scientists of the Global Footprint Network project, the annual resources of our planet (the amount of resources that can be used and then regenerated) were exhausted in only 7 months and 13 days. Scientists have been making such calculations since the 1970s, and every year they witness that the annual resources are being used up faster and faster. For example, in 2015, the amount of resources was exhausted six days earlier than in 2014, which certainly shows the need to promote the idea of rational use of resources and ensuring the development of countries without harming the environment. If a new economic policy is not implemented, according to the OECD's forecasts for 2050, the world's energy demand will increase by 80%. Table 1 shows how the energy demand of some countries will change.

No	States	According to the forecasts of 2050, the increase in energy demand
1.	South Africa	15%
2.	European countries	28%
3.	Japan	2,5%
4.	Mexico	12%

Greenhouse gas emissions will increase by 50% and worsen air pollution. Urban pollution will become the biggest problem by 2050. Drinking water pollution and poor sanitation are leading in this. Finally, the number of premature deaths caused by heavy air pollution reaches 3.6 million per year, and the share of China and India is significantly higher. The Earth's surface will shrink up to 10%, especially in the countries of Asia, Europe and South Africa. It is predicted that the area of natural forests will decrease by 13% (2). In order to prevent these global risks, the main attention should be focused on ecologization of the economy. There are a number of measures, such as the transition to the "green economy", introduction of eco-innovations and ecological investments. Innovation is a key factor for environmental efficiency and economic growth. Eco-innovation is any innovation that reduces the impact on the environment; it is the production of new products, the creation of systems and processes that conserve natural resources and emit minimal toxic substances

When analyzed at the level of countries, Germany is one of the advanced countries in this field, which has created a zero-waste production cycle in introducing green principles to all sectors of the economy. Germany is a world leader in waste processing and recycling. In Germany, 23 percent of patented technologies belong to the environment, and more than 30 percent of companies in the field of wind and solar energy belong to German companies. The number of workers in German companies working in the green sector, i.e. in areas related to environment and climate protection (energy, transport, recycling, waste disposal, etc.), is approximately 2 million people or a total of 4.5 percent of the economically active population. Today, this indicator has a growing tendency. Sweden's experience in eco-innovation is important. Sweden is a world leader in the use of renewable energy and local fuel sources. When the list of "green" countries on the planet was developed by Yale University scientists, Sweden took the first place in this rating. Today, the country's government is actively pursuing a policy of introducing green principles in all areas of the economy. Energy efficiency and renewable energy sources are the main and priority directions, and the sphere of energy and environmental protection is brought to the policy level (11). In Sweden, 96% of household waste is disposed of, which is one of the highest rates in the world. Homeowners will be given tax benefits when switching to renewable energy sources. Also, the tax will be reduced for car owners who use environmentally friendly fuel for their cars. In addition, free parking spaces are offered in the city. The share of such cars in the country is increasing year by year. These, of course, belong to the group of additional measures that have a positive effect on the ecology of the country.

In order to increase the share of the green sector in the state economy, tax incentives such as accelerated depreciation, property tax or income tax reduction can be used, especially preferential loans and green can make investments in technologies. But it is not considered correct for the state to provide business subsidies to ensure environmental compatibility.

Instead, state authorities should expand private banks and insurance companies that reflect the criterion of focusing on environmental factors in stimulating the financial status of enterprises. That is, banks may require a list of environmental indicators before approving a loan, and insurance companies may draw up an identification declaration on environmental risks and measures to reduce them. Also, banks and insurance companies can offer preferential favorable contract terms for companies with high environmental efficiency. In "Green Business" practice, providing direct subsidies and providing free technical assistance to enterprises to ensure their initial participation and dissemination of information is very effective. However, at present, many countries do not have enough legal norms on financing for the introduction and promotion of "green practices". financial allocations to show help long-term eco-economic stability of enterprises.

Conclusion The world experience shows that the "green economy" stimulates regional development, social stability, and the increase of economic potential through the creation of new jobs in the "green economy" sectors (5). "Green economy" mainly helps economic development and ensures the growth of the gross domestic product, increase of the country's income, employment of the population, reduction of the level of unemployment in the country. At the same time, the transition to a "green economy" will reduce the risk of global threats such as climate change, the loss of minerals, and the scarcity of water resources. , when today's world civilization has gathered strength and reached the peak of its power, if all the countries of the world do not choose an ecologically oriented model for economic development, the entire planet will gradually decline and completely disappear under the conditions of globalization. we can come to the conclusion that there is a risk of going.

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